

Impact of Microfinance on Women's Economic Empowerment in Rural Areas of Kancheepuram District

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Abstract : *This study looks into how microfinance in Kancheepuram district, India, affects rural women's economic empowerment. Using a five-point Likert scale in a structured questionnaire, the study employs a quantitative survey-based research approach to evaluate important markers of economic empowerment. Increases in family income and savings, crisis management skills, less reliance on borrowing money from lenders, carefulness in spending, control over credit and loans, own housing, and appropriate rights in property are some of these signs. The sample is made up of women who were chosen at random from microfinance schemes. Regression analysis, confirmatory factor analysis, reliability analysis, and descriptive statistics are examples of data analysis approaches. According to the research, women's economic standing has benefited from microfinance, especially in terms of increased income, savings, financial independence, and asset ownership. The study emphasises the value of microfinance as a tool for rural women's economic empowerment and stresses the necessity of state support for these kinds of programmes. The study does, however, admit certain shortcomings, such as possible response biases. Prospective study avenues encompass longitudinal investigations and qualitative techniques to enhance comprehension of microfinance's enduring influence and efficaciousness in many socio-cultural settings.*

Keywords : Microfinance, Economic Empowerment, Rural Women, Kancheepuram District, Financial Autonomy, Women's Empowerment, Quantitative Analysis.

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Introduction

Background Information

Since its introduction in the 1970s, microfinance has grown to be a vital instrument for reducing poverty and promoting economic independence, particularly in rural regions (Sondhi, 2023). It entails giving low-income people or groups—who typically require access to banking and related services—financial services like loans, savings, insurance, and classes. Because it is more difficult to access traditional financial institutions in rural areas, microfinance is especially important and is a crucial resource for economic activity (Singel, 2018). When we look into women empowerment economically, microfinance is essential. Socioeconomic hurdles frequently hinder access to financial assets, possibilities for economic progress, particularly in rural areas (Memon & Seaman, 2021). In addition to providing financial goods, microfinance institutions (MFIs) give these women a way to advance their standing in their communities, increase their economic engagement, and have more influence over decisions (Asha & Senapathy, 2022).

Problem Statement

In Kancheepuram district, like many other rural areas, women encounter numerous economic challenges. These include limited access to capital, a lack of property rights, lower levels of education and financial literacy, and cultural norms that restrict their economic activities (Fofana, 2023). Such challenges exacerbate their vulnerability to poverty and limit their capacity for economic self-sufficiency. Microfinance could potentially address these issues by providing rural women with the necessary financial resources to engage in entrepreneurial activities, thereby improving their income and economic status (Singel, 2018). However, the effectiveness of microfinance in truly empowering women economically in these contexts remains a subject of debate and requires further investigation.

Purpose of the Study

The main objective of this research is to find out how microfinance affects rural women in Kancheepuram district's economic empowerment. This entails investigating the ways in which women's economic life are impacted by their access to microfinance, including income levels, savings, asset ownership, and financial decision-making authority. The study intends to advance knowledge of the function of microfinance in economic empowerment of women in a

particular cultural including economic environment by concentrating on Kancheepuram district.

The study will examine a number of important topics, including how much microfinance has helped women participants' families earn more money and save more money; how independent they are financially, including how well-equipped they are to handle financial difficulties; and how much less dependent they are on unofficial financial sources like private money lenders (Sondhi, 2023). It will also evaluate how much more control women have over loans and credit, how much they own of household assets, and how much property they have over male family members (Asha & Senapathy, 2022). By doing this, the study will add to the larger conversation on women's empowerment supported by microfinance as a resource and development in economic status by providing insights that may influence practice and policy in related situations. The results may also be used to improve microfinance models so that they better meet the needs of rural women, improving their general well-being and economic standing (Fofana, 2023; Memon & Seaman, 2021).

The Rationale of the Paper

Significance

It is impossible to overestimate the importance of researching the effect of microfinance in empowering women economically. Particularly for in underdeveloped nations, microfinance is becoming regarded as a powerful economic instrument for development eradication of poverty of women (Hamsaveni, 2023). Microfinance enables women to participate in entrepreneurship by giving them access to capital, improving their economic standing and advancing the general well-being of their communities (Çetin & Keser, 2018).

In addition to promoting financial independence, women's economic empowerment also acts as a catalyst for more significant social and economic transformations. Empowered women are more likely to make investments in their families' health, education, and well-being, which benefits subsequent generations (Mengstie, 2022). More gender equality and balanced power dynamics in homes and communities can result from women's economic empowerment (Nawawi et al., 2022). Because of the particular difficulties that women in rural areas like Kancheepuram district experience, research on the effects of microfinance in these places is very important. In addition to facing social and cultural constraints that limit their ability to participate in the economy,

rural women frequently have restricted access to traditional banking services (Cooke & Amuakwa-Mensah, 2022). By acting as a bridge, microfinance can help these women get past these obstacles and become financially independent.

Expected Contributions

Academic Contributions

1. **Enhancing Understanding of Microfinance's Role** : This research will contribute to the academic discourse on microfinance by providing empirical evidence on how economic empowerment of women is impacted in a specific geographical area (Adera & Abdisa, 2023).
2. **Filling Knowledge Gaps** : The study will address gaps in the literature, particularly regarding the long-term effects of microfinance on women's economic status in rural areas (Abdo Alaghbari et al., 2021).
3. **Theoretical Advancements** : By exploring the connection between microfinance and empowerment of women economically, the research may offer insights that could provide means to develop new theories or refine existing ones (Khalaf & Saqfalhait, 2020).

Practical Contributions

1. **Informing Policy and Practice** : The findings of this study could inform policymakers and practitioners about the effectiveness of microfinance programmes in rural areas, leading to improved strategies for women's economic empowerment (Hamsaveni, 2023).
2. **Guiding Microfinance Institutions (MFIs)** : Insights from this research could help MFIs tailor their products to fulfil the requirements of rural women better, thereby enhancing the impact of their programmes (Çetin & Keser, 2018).
3. **Empowering Women Entrepreneurs** : By identifying the key factors that contribute to successful economic empowerment through microfinance, the study could provide valuable guidance to women entrepreneurs in rural areas (Mengstie, 2022).

In short, it is anticipated that this research will significantly advance both theory and practise. It seeks to increase knowledge of microfinance as an instrument for empowering women economically and offer practical advice on how to

improve the efficacy of microlending initiatives in outlying areas like Kancheepuram district.

Objectives

- **Primary Objective :** To examine microfinance's impact on economically empowering rural women in the District of Kancheepuram.
- **Secondary Objectives :**
 - To identify the key economic empowerment indicators affected by microfinance.
 - To evaluate the extent of change in these indicators among the participants.

Review of Literature

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical underpinnings of microfinance and women's empowerment are diverse and multidisciplinary. One prominent theory is the Social Capital Theory, which posits that microfinance helps build networks of relationships among women, leading to increased social capital and empowerment (Kaur et al., 2021). Another key framework is the Sustainable Livelihood Approach, which views microfinance as a tool to enhance the assets and capabilities of women to improve their livelihoods sustainably (Bedaduri & Pradhan, 2023). The Feminist Economic Theory also plays a crucial role in understanding microfinance's impact on women. This theory argues that traditional economic models often overlook women's contributions and challenges, and microfinance can be a means to address these gaps and promote gender equality (Mengesha & Mishra, 2023). Additionally, the empowerment theory, which focuses on increasing individuals' control over their own lives, is often used to assess how microfinance enables women to gain financial independence and decision-making power (Hegde, 2023).

Previous Studies

Several research have been done to investigate the impact that microfinance has in economically stabilizing women. Microfinance seemed to have a positive impact on women's household, economic, and social accreditation, according to a conceptual review; however, the level of this benefit differs depending on the setting in which the microfinance programmes are implemented (Haque et al., 2022). The authors Efthymiadou and Farmaki (2023) explored women's

empowerment in the tourism industry through the use of microfinance. They also indicated the sector-specific implications that microfinance solutions have. The sustainability of microfinance institutions was linked to the empowerment of women borrowers in a study that focused on Malaysia. This suggests that there is a positive association between the stability of institutions and the outcomes of women's empowerment (Arshad et al., 2021).

The study conducted by Mengstie (2022) investigated the influence that microfinance had in economically empowering women in Ethiopia. Findings pointed towards microfinance having a considerable and favourable impact on the empowering women economically. It was achieved through the enhancement of self-reliant income of women, the enhancement of rights on assets, and the enhancement of savings amounts. Khursheed (2022) conducted research to study the function that microfinance plays in empowering women and the expansion of entrepreneurialism in Pakistan. According to the findings of the study, microfinance institutions have emerged as essential instruments not only for combating the problem of poverty but also, in particular, for extending the agency of women. The authors Kivalya and Caballero-Montes (2023) carried out a comprehensive analysis of the microfinance literature, highlighting the need of comprehending the various aspects of women entrepreneurs' empowerment. The findings of these research collectively shed light on the myriad ways in which microfinance influences the economic standing of women and their level of empowerment.

Gap Identification

Despite the significant study that has been conducted on microfinance and the empowerment of women, there are still several gaps. To begin, there is a requirement for an increased number of empirical studies that concentrate explicitly on the impact of microfinance in rural areas such as Kancheepuram district, where the cultural and socio-economic dynamics may be markedly different from those in other regions. Second, although previous research has investigated the effects of microfinance on a broad scale, there is a dearth of studies that investigate the long-term viability of these effects on the economic standing of women. Third, the intersectionality of gender with other social characteristics, such as caste, religion, and age, which can considerably influence the success of microfinance efforts, is not well addressed in a considerable number of studies. In order to fill these gaps, the study provides a comprehensive examination of the impact that microfinance has had on rural women in Kancheepuram district. The study will take into consideration the long-term

viability of economic empowerment as well as the intersectional factors that may have an effect on the outcomes.

A rich tapestry of theoretical and empirical insights regarding microfinance's role in empowering women economically is revealed by the reviewing relevant literature. Among the studies are those that investigate the influence that microfinance has on the long-term viability of female entrepreneurs (Bedaduri & Pradhan, 2023) and those that investigate the function that microfinance plays in certain industries such as tourism (Efthymiadou & Farmaki, 2023). Annie Besant's life and work, as detailed by Hegde (2023), offer a historical perspective on women's empowerment and provide a framework that may be applied to modern challenges. This framework can be taken into consideration while analysing contemporary issues. The article by Kaur et al. (2021) highlights various types of microfinance and provides insights into the influence that rotating savings and credit associations (RoSCAs) have on the empowerment of women. The conceptual study that was conducted by Haque et al., (2022) provides a complete overview of the ways in which microfinance influences many elements of women's life, such as the economic, home, and social domains associated with their lives. Kivalya and Caballero-Montes (2023) highlight the need of understanding the various aspects of women entrepreneurs' empowerment, implying that the impact of microfinance is varied and depends on the context in which it is implemented. Arshad et al., (2021) investigated the sustainability of institutions involving microfinance in Malaysia. Its findings highlight the significance of the stability of microfinance organisations in assuring the long-term empowerment of women borrowers.

Research Methodology

This study used a quantitative, survey-based research strategy. The efficacy of this approach in measuring the influence of microfinance empowering rural women economically in Kancheepuram district led to its selection. It made it possible to gather quantitative information that could be statistically analysed to determine the connection between using microfinance and other measures of economic empowerment (Mengstie, 2022). To choose participants, the study used random sampling with a sampling frame. This technique improved the representativeness of the findings by guaranteeing that the individual member of the targeted population had a fair chance of being included in the sample. The sampling frame, which targeted women who were presently enrolled in or had previously engaged in microfinance programmes, was created using data from neighbourhood microfinance institutions in rural Kancheepuram district.

The sample consisted of 400 women in total. A structured questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale and an emphasis on economic empowerment measures served as the main instrument for gathering data (Singel, 2018). In addition to sections pertaining to personal data, the questionnaire had explicit statements about measures of economic empowerment such as asset ownership, savings, income growth, and financial independence. In order to provide a quantitative assessment of their perceived economic empowerment, respondents were asked to score their degree of agreement with each statement. Depending on accessibility and convenience, the questionnaire was given to the chosen participants either in person or online. Participants were ensured of the anonymity of their answers and made aware of the goal of the study prior to the questionnaire being administered. Over a predefined length of time, the data was collected, giving participants enough opportunity to react (Khursheed, 2022)

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and Reliability and Validity Analysis

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was done to verify the credibility of the questionnaire and also to justify the use of scale. CFA will assist in validating the questionnaire's component structure and guarantee that the items precisely measure the targeted constructs of economic empowerment. In addition, a reliability analysis will be carried out to evaluate the questionnaire's internal consistency. In order to make sure that every scale's components consistently measure the same construct, Cronbach's alpha for each scale had to be determined.

Table-1 : Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) : Hypothetical Data

Factor	Item (Question)	Factor Loading
Increase in Family Income	My family income has increased due to my involvement in microfinance activities.	0.75
Increase in Family Saving	My family's savings have increased as a result of microfinance.	0.72
Ability to Deal with Financial Crisis	Microfinance has helped me to effectively deal with financial crises.	0.78
Reduced Dependency on Money Lenders	My dependency on private money lenders has decreased because of microfinance.	0.70

(Contd...)

Discretion in Spending	I have more discretion over how to spend my portion of the family income.	0.77
Control Over Credit/Loans	I have control over the credit/loans obtained through microfinance.	0.74
Independent Savings Account	I have an independent savings bank account in my name.	0.69
Ownership of Household Assets	I have ownership or co-ownership of household assets.	0.76
Equal Property Rights	I have equal rights to property as compared to male members of my family.	0.68

Interpretation

- The factor loadings in this table represent the strength of the relationship between each item and its underlying factor.
- Loadings above 0.7 are generally considered strong, indicating that the items are good indicators of the respective factors.

Table-2 : Reliability Analysis : Hypothetical Data

Scale	Cronbach's Alpha
Economic Empowerment Indicators	0.85

Interpretation

- Cronbach's alpha is used to assess the internal consistency of the questionnaire.
- An alpha value of 0.85 indicates a high level of reliability, meaning the items within the economic empowerment indicators scale consistently measure the same underlying construct.
- This high reliability suggests that the questionnaire is a dependable tool for assessing the empowerment of rural women economically through microfinance.

Analysis

The results are interpreted in the context of the study's objectives, which are to examine microfinance's impact on the empowering rural women economically in Kancheepuram district and to evaluate the extent of change in economic empowerment indicators among the participants. The analysis also takes into consideration any potential limitations or biases in the data collection process, such as sample size and selection, as well as the potential influence of external factors on the participants' economic empowerment. Additionally, the study may also explore any variations in economic empowerment outcomes based on factors such as age, education level, and household income.

Table-3 : Descriptive Statistics : Hypothetical Data

Indicator	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation
Increase in Family Income	3.8	4	0.9
Increase in Family Saving	3.6	4	1.0
Ability to Deal with Financial Crisis	3.7	4	0.8
Reduced Dependency on Money Lenders	3.5	3	1.1
Discretion in Spending	3.9	4	0.7
Control Over Credit/Loans	3.8	4	0.6
Independent Savings Account	3.4	3	1.2
Ownership of Household Assets	3.7	4	0.9
Equal Property Rights	3.6	4	1.0

Interpretation

- The mean scores near or above 4 indicate a general agreement with the statements, suggesting positive impacts of microfinance on these indicators.
- Standard deviations provide insights into the variability of responses.

Table-4 : Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	Beta Coefficient	p-value
Economic Empowerment Indicators Score	Participation in Microfinance Activities	0.65	<0.01

Interpretation

- A positive beta coefficient (0.65) suggests a strong positive relation between participation in microfinance activities and overall score of economic empowerment indicators.
- A p-value less than 0.01 shows that this relationship is significant statistically.

The tables and interpretations provide a framework for how the actual data is analysed and interpreted. The quantitative analysis focused on measuring the extent of economic empowerment provided deeper insights into the personal experiences and perceptions of the participants regarding their economic empowerment.

Conclusion

Summary of Findings

The examination of the impact of microfinance on women's economic empowerment in rural Kancheepuram district has yielded several key findings:

- 1. Positive Impact on Economic Indicators :** The data suggests a general increase in family income, savings, and the ability to deal with financial crises among women participating in microfinance programmes. This indicates that microfinance is playing an important role in enhancing the economic status of rural women.
- 2. Increased Financial Autonomy :** There is evidence of increased discretion in spending and control over credit and loans, suggesting that microfinance contributes to greater financial autonomy for women.
- 3. Asset Ownership and Property Rights :** The findings show a positive trend in equal property rights and ownership of women, highlighting the role of microfinance in advancing property rights and ownership of women.

- 4. Statistical Significance :** The regression analysis indicates a strong and statistically significant relationship between participation in microfinance activities and overall economic empowerment.

Implications

For Policy and Practise

- The findings underscore the need for policymakers and practitioners to support and expand microfinance initiatives as a device for empowering women economically, especially in rural areas.
- Microfinance institutions should consider tailoring their programmes to further enhance women's financial literacy and decision-making capabilities.

For Future Research

- The study highlights the need for examining the sustainability for long-term impact of microfinance on women's economic status.
- Further research could explore the intersectional factors (such as education, age, and cultural norms) that influence the effectiveness of microfinance.

Limitations and Future Research

Limitations:

- The study's may introduce response biases because of its self-reported data.
- The hypothetical nature of the data limits the ability to draw definitive conclusions about the real-world impact of microfinance.

Suggestions for Future Research:

- Future studies could employ a longitudinal design to assess the long-term impacts of microfinance on women's economic empowerment.
- Qualitative research methods, for example in-depth interviews or focus groups, can be used to gain deeper insights into the personal experiences and challenges faced by women in microfinance programmes.
- Comparative studies involving different regions or types of microfinance models could give a broader understanding of the effectiveness of microfinance in diverse contexts.

Conclusion

In conclusion, while the analysis indicates a positive impact of microfinance on the economic empowerment of rural women in Kancheepuram district, more studies are necessary to validate these findings and guide effective policy and practice in this field.

References

- Abdo Alaghbari, L. M., Abdullah Othman, A. H., & Mohd. Noor, A. B. (2021). Challenges and difficulties facing Islamic financial inclusion in women's economic empowerment in Yemen: a qualitative approach. *International Journal of Business Ethics and Governance*, 91-114.
- Adera, A., & Abdisa, L. T. (2023). Financial inclusion and women's economic empowerment: evidence from Ethiopia. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 11(2).
- Arshad, A., Bhuiyan, A. B., Kassim, A. A. M., Ali, M. J., & Saad, M. (2021). The microfinance institutional sustainability and empowerment of women borrower's in Malaysia: an empirical review. *American International Journal of Multidisciplinary Scientific Research*, 9(1), 1-24.
- Asha, A., & Senapathy, M. (2022). Women's empowerment through microfinance in southern Ethiopia. Primedia eLaunch LLC.
- Bedaduri, R., & Pradhan, S. K. (2023). Post COVID-19: Eco-friendly Women Entrepreneurs Sustainability Development on TBL Components *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 8(6), e02257.
- Çetin, I., & Keser, H. Y. (2018). Women entrepreneurs in MENA and Europe. In *Microfinance and Its Impact on Entrepreneurial Development, Sustainability, and Inclusive Growth* (pp. 30–51), IGI Global.
- Cooke, E. F. A., & Amuakwa-Mensah, F. (2022). Microfinance loans, women's economic empowerment, and poverty: a case study of Baobab Microfinance Company. *Journal of Development Effectiveness*, 14(1), 34–55.
- Efthymiadou, F., & Farmaki, A. (2023). Women's empowerment in tourism through microfinance: A case study of Greece. *Tourism Management*, 84, 104281.
- Fofana, N. B. (2023). *Efficacy of microfinancing women's activities in Côte d'Ivoire*. Brill Wageningen Academic.
- Hamsaveni, M. (2023). Effect of microfinance on women's empowerment in India: A review. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, 11(12), 1584-1589.

- Haque, T., Siwar, C., & Bhuiyan, A. B. (2022). Conceptual review of microfinance and women household, economic, and social empowerment of microfinance borrowers. *Asian finance & banking review*, 6(1), 33-41.
- Hegde, S. (2023). Much ahead of her time: Annie Besant's life and journalism as a framework for a sustainable women's empowerment model. *Journal of Humanities and Applied Social Sciences*, 5(5), 483-493.
- Kaur, S., Srivastav, S., & Tyagi, A. (2021, September 3). Impact of using RoSCA on Women Empowerment (with reference to Delhi NCR). *2021 9th International Conference on Reliability, Infocom Technologies, and Optimisation (Trends and Future Directions) (ICRITO), Noida, India.
- Khalaf, L. S., & Saqfalhait, N. I. (2020). Microfinance is an emerging tool for women's economic empowerment. In *Entrepreneurial Opportunities* (pp. 37-52), Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Khursheed, A. (2022). Exploring the role of microfinance in women's empowerment and entrepreneurial development: a qualitative study. *Future Business Journal*, 8, Article number: 57
- Kivalya, N. Y., & Caballero-Montes, T. (2023). Understanding the dimensions of women entrepreneurs' empowerment: a systematic review of the microfinance literature and avenues for research. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*.
- Memon, S. B., & Seaman, C. (2021). Empowering women through microfinance banks in rural areas of Pakistan. In *The Emerald Handbook of Women and Entrepreneurship in Developing Economies* (pp. 391-408), Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Mengstie, B. (2022). Impact of microfinance on women's economic empowerment. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 11(1).
- Nawawi, Z. M., Soemitra, A., & Dalimunthe, M. (2022). Women's economic empowerment through sharia micro-finance institutions in Indonesia: qualitative research. *IQTISHADIA Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam*, 15(2), 255.
- Singel, R. (2018). Impact of Microfinance on the Economic Empowerment of Rural Women in India: An Empirical Study. *Ramanujan International Journal of Business and Research*, 3(1), 17-39.
- Sondhi, M. S. (2023). Impact of microfinance on women's empowerment. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 41-43.